

Derivation of Equation for the Variation of Viscosity of Dilute Solutions of Strong Electrolytes According to Cube-root of Concentration

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In previous publications it has been shown that κ (kappa) of the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes requires modification. An expression for the modified kappa, denoted by κ_m , has been deduced and the effective ionic diameter, a has been included in it. In the concentration range of an electrolyte solution, in which, a (the effective ionic diameter) remains constant, κ_m varies as the cube-root of concentration. Using this modified κ_m an equation has been deduced which can satisfactorily account for the variation of viscosity of solutions of the strong electrolytes with their concentration up to about 0.1 M. The equation indicates the possibility of determining a , from viscosity measurements of strong electrolyte solutions.

VISCOSITY of the aqueous solutions of strong electrolytes has been investigated, at different temperatures, covering a wide range of concentration. Among those who carried out investigations in the region of high concentration mention may be made of Vand¹, Suryanarayana and Venkatesan², Thomas³, Moulik^{4,5}, and Breslau and Miller⁶. Viscosity of strong electrolyte solutions in the region of low concentration has been measured carefully by Gruneisen⁷, Jones *et al.*⁸⁻¹⁰, Wolfenden *et al.*^{11,12}, Chakravarti and Prasad^{13,14} and others^{15,16}.

Jones and Dole⁹ have found that the relative viscosity η/η_0 of many strong electrolyte solutions varies upto about 0.1M according to equation (1).

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

A and B are constants in equation (1) and the term $A\sqrt{C}$ has been attributed to interionic attraction. The observation of the authors mentioned above are in agreement with this equation. It may, however, be mentioned that $A\sqrt{C}$ has been found to be zero for solutions of non-electrolytes, like sucrose⁹, of mercuric chloride¹⁴ and also of aminoacids¹⁷, like alanine, at different values of pH.

Derivation of the equations :

Falkenhagen *et al.*^{18,19} have shown that A in equation (1) can be calculated by using an equation deduced by them on the basis of the Debye-Hückel theory of interionic attraction. Equation (1) may be written as

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + (A/\beta)\beta\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1a)$$

$$= 1 + (A/\beta)\kappa + BC \quad (2)$$

where, $\beta\sqrt{C} = \kappa$ and for a 1 : 1 electrolyte $\beta = 0.3291 \times 10^8$ at 25°.

It has been shown by the author^{20,21} in previous publications that κ of the Debye-Hückel theory should be modified. The modified kappa, denoted by κ_m should be expressed as $\kappa_m = (\alpha\beta/\sqrt{a})[C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}]$, where C_0 is a constant and α and β are also constants which can be calculated from theory, and a represents the effective ionic diameter. For 1 : 1 electrolytes $\alpha = 1.22$ and $\beta = 0.3291 \times 10^8$ as already stated. Substituting κ_m in place of κ in equation (2) and simplifying we get the following expressions.

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + (A\alpha/\sqrt{a})[C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}] + BC \quad (3)$$

$$= 1 + g[C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}] + BC \quad (3a)$$

where, $g = (A\alpha/\sqrt{a})$. C_0 in equation (3) or (3a) represents that concentration of an electrolyte at which inter-ionic attraction disappears. It is very small but not zero.

In the following section, equation (3a) has been subjected to test using the data collected from the literature on LiCl, NH₄Cl, LiBr, LiI, KBr, KI, KNO₃, K₂SO₄ and BaCl₂.

It may be mentioned that in a previous publication²², it has been shown that equation (3a) holds good for solutions of KCl and NaCl upto 0.1M.

Processing of data to verify equation (3a) : The values of the constants g and B in equation (3a) have been found by plotting $[(\eta/\eta_0) - (1 - gC_0^{1/3})]/C^{1/3}$ vs $C^{2/3}$, neglecting at first $gC_0^{1/3}$ which is very small compared to the other terms. The intercept and slope of the straight line give approximate values of g and B †.

† The approximate values of g and B are now used to determine $C_0^{1/3}$ from the experimental data of η/η_0 . Next, $[(\eta/\eta_0) - (1 - gC_0^{1/3})]/C^{1/3}$ is plotted against $C^{2/3}$ to get improved values of g and B . These improved values of g and B are used to get improved value of $C_0^{1/3}$. The process is repeated until the final values of $C_0^{1/3}$, g and B give the desired fit between the observed and the calculated values of η/η_0 .

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF η/η_0 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THE ELECTROLYTE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C M	Values of η/η_0		C M	Values of η/η_0	
		Obs.	Calcd.		Obs.	Calcd.
LiCl Ref. 12 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0035$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.048$ $B=0.142$	0.00707	1.00145	1.00151	0.08462	1.01336	1.01338
	0.02321	1.00486	1.00490	0.1111	1.01721	1.01729
	0.05641	1.00919	1.00918			
LiBr Ref. 12 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0034$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.040$ $B=0.119$	0.00843	1.00164	1.00159	0.04147	1.00600	1.00601
	0.01686	1.00283	1.00278	0.04921	1.00703	1.00700
	0.02529	1.00386	1.00391	0.05695	1.00790	1.00798
	0.03372	1.00503	1.00509	0.07181	1.00984	1.00986
LiI Ref. 12 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0032$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.034$ $B=0.08$	0.009863	1.00130	1.00136	0.04811	1.00503	1.00490
	0.01973	1.00227	1.00233	0.05737	1.00559	1.00572
	0.02959	1.00328	1.00325	0.07475	1.00722	1.00722
	0.03885	1.00397	1.00408			
KBr Ref. 8 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0025$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.037$ $B=-0.044$	0.001	1.00010	1.00011	0.02	0.99972	0.99970
	0.002	1.00010	1.00013	0.05	0.99874	0.99862
	0.005	1.00009	1.00011			
	0.01	0.99998	1.00000	0.10	0.99678	0.99666
KI Ref. 12 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.002$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.057$ $B=-0.081$	0.00275	0.99994	0.99997	0.01006	0.99716	0.99733
	0.00544	0.99950	0.99980	0.05929	0.99574	0.99586
	0.01102	0.99957	0.99944	0.08773	0.99350	0.99359
	0.02203	0.99875	0.99866	0.09696	0.99296	0.99291
	0.02965	0.99775	0.99790			
KNO ₃ Ref. 8 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0022$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.024$ $B=-0.047$	0.001	1.00012	1.00012	0.020	0.99964	0.99960
	0.002	1.00013	1.00013	0.050	0.99845	0.99841
	0.005	1.00012	1.00009	0.100	0.99623	0.99627
	0.010	0.99995	0.99995			
NH ₄ Cl Ref. 8 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.00265$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.083$ $B=-0.0076$	0.002	1.00020	1.00023	0.05	1.00054	1.00051
	0.005	1.00031	1.00033			
	0.010	1.00045	1.00041	0.100	1.00036	1.00038
	0.020	1.00051	1.00048			
BaCl ₂ Ref. 9 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0075$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.012$ $B=0.237$	0.005	1.0025	1.0024	0.050	1.0147	1.0145
	0.010	1.0037	1.0039	0.100	1.0271	1.0271
	0.020	1.0082	1.0080			
K ₂ SO ₄ Ref. 10 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.0065$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.032$ $B=0.211$	0.0005	1.00039	1.00041	0.020	1.00586	1.00578
	0.001	1.00062	1.00065			
	0.002	1.00103	1.00103	0.050	1.01281	0.01274
	0.005	1.00198	1.00196			
	0.010	1.00334	1.00331	0.100	1.02380	1.02391

TABLE 2—VALUES OF η/η_0 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THE ELECTROLYTE SOLUTIONS AT 35°

Miscellaneous	C M	Values of η/η_0		C M	Values of η/η_0	
		Obs.	Calcd.		Obs.	Calcd.
BaCl ₂ Ref. 13 Eqn. (3a) $g=0.007$ $C_0^{1/2}=0.012$ $B=0.315$	0.0015	1.0012	1.0012	0.010	1.0045	1.0046
	0.0020	1.0014	1.0014	0.020	1.0085	1.0082
	0.0025	1.0017	1.0017	0.030	1.0117	1.0115
	0.0030	1.0021	1.0019	0.040	1.0146	1.0149
	0.0040	1.0025	1.0023	0.050	1.0180	1.0182
	0.0050	1.0029	1.0027	0.100	1.0307	1.0347

In Tables 1 and 2 under the head miscellaneous in column 1 are mentioned the electrolyte, the reference whose data have been selected, the equation used to calculate η/η_0 and the values of the constants in the equation. In the columns 2 and 5, C represents the concentration in mol dm^{-3} .

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables 1 and 2 that the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of η/η_0 is fairly satisfactory upto $C=0.1 M$ for the 1 : 1 electrolytes and upto $C=0.05 M$ for the 2 : 1 electrolyte BaCl_2 used at 35° .

A comparison of the values of g and B in equation (3a) for BaCl_2 at 25 and 35° shows that g increases slightly but B increases markedly with the increase of temperature. According to Kaminsky¹⁶, g should decrease with the increase of temperature. Further investigation on this point using different types of strong electrolytes is desirable.

An examination of the data on the halides of Li^+ and K^+ recorded in Table 1 leads to the conclusion that B is approximately an additive property of the ions of the electrolytes as was first suggested by Cox and Wolfenden¹¹. The effects of electrical charge and of hydration of ions on B have also been discussed by a number of authors^{12, 23, 24}. The B of equation (1) differs from B of equation (3a) and evaluation of the latter from theory should now be attempted.

It has been found that variation of equivalent conductance, λ of KBr solutions²⁵ in the concentration range 13.949×10^{-4} to $71.696 \times 10^{-4} M$ is accurately represented by the equation, $\lambda = 153.76 - 49(c)^{1/2}$. The value of the effective ionic diameter found by using this conductance equation* and that found by using equation (3a) taking $A = 0.0049$ (Ref. 26) and $\alpha = 1.22$ (as stated already) are 5.69 and $5.71 \text{ \AA}$, respectively. Hence, the agreement

between these two values of a may be considered satisfactory.

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* According to theory, $49 = \frac{mG}{\sqrt{a}}$ and $mG = 11610$ for KBr .